

From Cells to Pixels: Bridging Biologists and Image Analysts Through a Common Language

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Abstract

Bioimaging has transformed our understanding of biological processes, yet extracting meaningful information from complex datasets remains a challenge, particularly for early career scientists. This paper proposes a simplified, systematic approach to bioimage analysis, focusing on categorizing commonly observed structures and shapes, and providing relevant analysis methods. Our approach includes illustrative examples and a visual flowchart, enabling researchers to define analysis objectives clearly. By understanding the diversity of bioimage structures and aligning them with appropriate analysis approaches, the framework empowers researchers to navigate bioimage datasets more efficiently. It also aims to foster a common language between researchers and analysts, thereby enhancing mutual understanding and facilitating effective communication.

Visual abstract: An overview of the decision tree for identifying families of image analysis methods depending on the type of structure within the image.

Abbreviations

BIII: bioimage informatics index
 MSD: mean-square displacement
 NEUBIAS: Network of European BioImage Analysts
 RAG: region adjacency graph
 ROI: region of interest

Keywords

Microscopy, Bioimage analysis, Shape analysis, Bioimaging

Introduction

Bioimaging has revolutionized our understanding of biological processes. When studying these processes, the acquisition of images, for example using microscopy, is merely the first step. As microscopy techniques evolve and datasets become more complex, one crucial challenge is extracting meaningful information. Often, it falls on early career scientists to set analysis goals, explore potential solutions, set up complete analysis workflows, and interpret the data. These workflows require a diversity of skills for interconnecting the biological question, the specificities of the image acquisition device(s), the mathematical concepts of image analysis, and the knowledge of relevant and available software.

Imaging core facility staff increasingly find themselves getting similar questions from the users of their facility about bioimage analysis approaches and problems. In response, many core facilities invest time and effort in educating staff on digital image analysis and training them with diverse software tools to provide more comprehensive help and support. While many image analysis reference resources are available¹⁻³, they often target an audience with a strong background in mathematics or signal processing. Additionally, research groups may hire professional image analysts, mainly computer scientists, to assist biologists with bioimage analysis questions. Finally, the number of specialized core facilities dedicated to providing image analysis as a service has increased during the past few years.^{4,5}

The increasing interaction between biological and computational scientists emphasizes the importance of establishing a common language between domain specialists and bioimage analysts. Researchers must be able to clearly articulate the scientific problems they seek to address through bioimage analysis. Conversely, analysts need to be able to process this information and provide results in a manner that is not only accurate and reliable but also interpretable by researchers in their respective fields. Therefore, fostering a shared language and bridging the gap between the world of image analysis and biological research is crucial.

A large number of efforts have been undertaken to bridge this gap. Several reviews have emphasized the importance of acquisition setup to be able to relate images to quantitative information⁶⁻⁹, including good practices for meta-data¹⁰. A large literature was also devoted to the design of relevant image analysis workflow, including pre-processing, segmentation, and analysis steps^{6,7,11-14}. As the establishment of a common language was crucial to bridge people from different communities, ontologies have been developed and made available¹⁵⁻¹⁸. A large number of bio-image analysis software have been developed, making it necessary to classify and reference them¹⁹⁻²². Also, the Network of European BioImage Analysts (NEUBIAS) project allowed to gather and organize some of these efforts, in training schools²³, bio-image analysis workflow centered books^{16,17}, and the bioimage informatics index (BIII) database¹⁸.

Here, in addition to these numerous efforts, we propose a simple general approach, to help identify which image analysis methods could be relevant for a given archetype of bioimage data. We first categorize structures commonly observed in Bioimage data into different types related to image analysis domains. Each type is illustrated with a series of examples that associate a biological structure with an acquisition scale. Once categories are identified, we provide a list of methods, illustrated with application examples in biology, that apply to images related to each category. As some families of methods are more common in domains different from biology, such as material sciences or mathematics, we try to provide examples from biological studies. Finally, we propose a visual flowchart that summarizes the choices between biological structure type and relevant image analysis method. This way, the information is

visually comprehensible and easily digestible, and ultimately facilitates the common understanding between researchers and bioimage analysts. ²⁰

While we will not discuss here the initial processing steps that are often necessary before undertaking bioimage analysis, it is important to highlight their importance. These steps are highly dependent on the datasets and may include several of the following steps: noise removal, registration, filtering, and segmentation methods, among other things. Segmentation by itself is one of the most important topics that any image analyst deals with at some point in their careers and plays a vital role in preparing images for more advanced analysis. These steps are integral to ensure the accuracy, reliability, and reproducibility of the analysis results and, therefore, should not be overlooked. In addition, we do not specify specific software to use for each category as this is a preference of each analyst and depends on the size of the data in addition to the type and the resources available. Moreover, there have been other efforts in categorizing and suggesting tools per category that are already available.

With this in mind, we aim to help change the approach early career researchers take towards bioimage datasets. We encourage biologists to adopt the mindset of image analysts to perceive the global picture of bioimage analysis steps. This minimal visual chart of bioimage structures and analysis types is designed not just as a reference but as a tool that empowers researchers to engage in effective communication with image analysts, ensuring mutual understanding. Furthermore, it will help researchers clearly define their image analysis objectives and comprehend the initial steps necessary to achieve their goals.

Types of structures observed in Bioimage data

This section classifies and categorizes the diverse types of structures one might encounter in bioimaging based on what they look like. The categorisation is based on the morphology of the structure, as this will drive the choice of relevant methods for image quantification. The different structure types considered here are summarized in Figure 1. For each category, we provide several bioimage examples to help associate a biological object with a structure type.

As seen in Figure 1, the simplest form of the bioimage structures, compact regions evolve into complex regions as their geometric complexity increases with the addition of curves, angles, spikes, and varying degrees of smoothness. These complex regions, when aggregated within a limited field of view, form porous media. Curvilinear regions represent a transformation where compact shapes are elongated. Networks consist of either multiple interconnected curvilinear regions or are derived from image processing, e.g., skeletonization of porous media, illustrating the connectivity within the structure. Smaller elements within this framework are identified as point patterns, which are either a collection of small regions or computationally derived from compact regions, junctions, or extremities within networks. This relational mapping underscores

the diversity and complexity of shapes derived from biological structures, highlighting the various analysis perspectives that can be adopted based on their appearance and the analysis goals.

Figure 1: Overview of the different types of structures that can be considered for setting up an image analysis workflow, and relationships between them.

Dashed arrows correspond to conceptual change, solid arrows correspond to changes that can be obtained by image processing algorithm. Most cases concern regions. Regions can exhibit various morphologies: small and numerous, elongated, complex... When regions are very small, they can be considered as point patterns. When regions are elongated, they may be assimilated to a single curve. Thin regions with very complex shapes can be considered to be a network structure. Complex regions with a limited field of view may be better described as porous media.

Regions

In many cases, the biological question leads us to consider one or several distinct **regions**, or regions of interest (ROI), within an image. Most of the time, regions considered in bioimaging correspond to nuclei, as they are easy to identify from images (Fig. 2B), or to cells when their outline can be distinguished (Fig. 2A,B,E). Other examples of regions include organelles within cells, or, at a larger scale, organs (liver, kidney, plant stem or leaf) (Fig. 2C), or whole organisms (Fig. 2D,F).

From an image analyst's point of view, a region is a set of connected pixels that share common properties, such as the same range of intensity or the same spectral characteristics. Regions may also be represented by a geometric shape such as a rectangle, line, or polygon. There are also often some "hidden" assumptions about the shape: a region is often expected to have a significant area.

In practice, the image analysis approaches often differ depending on the morphology of the region, and different sub-cases may be distinguished.

In many cases, the region is assumed to have a "regular" shape, i.e. to be nearly convex. Examples include typical nuclei as observed in optical or confocal microscopy (Fig. 2B), cultured cells with smooth perimeters observed with light or fluorescence imaging, some organs in the human or animal body e.g. liver, kidney, and heart among other things.

Regions may also be strongly elongated, with a geometry that can be assimilated to a thick or thin curve. In such cases one often wants to consider the medial axis of the region.

It is common to consider regions with a more complex geometry than a nucleus. A typical example consists in neurons observed with light microscopy, that present a complex geometry with many elongated and ramified dendrites.

Examples:

- Nuclei as observed in optical or confocal microscopy
- "Regular" cells observed in optical imaging
- Lysosomes, often defined as spherical vesicles
- Some organs in the human or animal body: liver, kidney, heart...
- xylem vessels within wood ²⁴
- Filopodia
- Lamellipodia
- Cell membrane observed within a section
- Microtubules of plant cells e.g. cortical microtubules^{25,26}
- Microtubules of animal cells ²⁷
- Neurons
- Leaves with complex shapes

Figure 2: Examples of regions in bioimaging studies. (A) Automated segmentation of breast cancer nuclei from H&E stained tissue section (from ²⁸). (B) Segmentation of nuclei outlines from fluorescence microscopy image (from ²⁹). (C) Cells from distinct tissues are identified on electron microscopy images (from ³⁰). (D) Segmentation of various organelles within a cell from TEM images (from ³¹). (E) Joint segmentation of cells and nuclei in synthetic 3D data structures (from ³²). (F) Delineation of the contour of a leaf. (G) Identification of the contour of a nematode (from ³³).

Networks (and curve-like objects)

Many biological structures such as neurons, vessels, or membranes appear as thin objects, looking like a curve with constant thickness range, or an interconnection of curves. The interconnection of curves may form a network-like structure. In terms of acquisition, it may be necessary to acquire tile scans over larger areas to capture the entire network. In such cases, one is more interested in the interconnection pattern of the network than its global morphometry. From an image analyst's point of view, networks are defined by a range of metrics, including branching, connectivity density, nodes and junction distribution and branch lengths, all of which provide insights into the functionality of networks or comparing phenotypes.

Examples of networks:

- Neurons: Studying neuronal networks, their branching and synapse formation gives insights into neuronal development, plasticity, and various neurological conditions ³⁴
- Plant roots: The architecture of these structures serves critical functions including water and nutrient uptake.
- Blood vessels: Studying vascular network, with its arteries, veins and capillaries, assists in understanding angiogenesis, vascular diseases, and tissue perfusion ³⁵
- Ophthalmology: retinal vessel network from fundus screening ^{36,37}
- Lymphatic networks: They play crucial roles in immune responses.
- Cell cytoskeleton: these filamentous networks maintain cellular structure, aid in motility, and play roles in intracellular transport and signaling. Visualizing their dynamics and organization is vital for cell biology, particularly in understanding cell division, migration, and mechanotransduction.
- Trachea: In insects, these structures are involved in the transport of gasses.
- Mycelium: In fungi, these structures are complex underground networks involved in nutrient absorption.
- Endoplasmic reticulum (in 2D images)
- Vasculature network within plant tissues ³⁸

Figure 3: Examples of image structures representing networks, or collections of curvilinear regions. (A) dendritic network of a neuron ³⁴. (B) root network of maize (from ³⁹). (C) Angiogenesis in the embryonic hindbrain (from ³⁵). (D) actin network in plants (from ⁴⁰) (E) venation network in a grapevine leaf (from ⁴¹).

Point patterns

When considering a large number of small regions, an extreme case occurs when the size of the regions becomes negligible or irrelevant, and each region can be assimilated to a point corresponding to its position. Examples include (small) organelles within a cell, or proteins appearing as fluorescent dots. Instead of regions, observations correspond to a collection of punctual observations, also called a point

pattern. When considering such point patterns, different questions may arise: what is the number (or the numerical density) of the points? Are they located according to another structure (on the boundary of an organ, around a given region, parallel to a surface...)? Are they regions within the image where the points are more numerous? Do the points interact with each other, to form clusters, or on the contrary do they tend to repulse each other? When imaging proteins, a common question is to quantify the colocalization of two proteins. Object-based colocalization analysis quantifies how two structures are co-located within the same spatial region of a cell or tissue. This can provide insights into interactions, co-functionality, or co-regulation within cellular processes.

Examples of point patterns:

- Synaptic vesicles/puncta: In neuronal studies, the distribution of these vesicles can offer insights into synaptic strength, plasticity, and changes associated with various conditions or treatments..
- Cell receptors: The clustering or distribution of specific receptors on a cell surface can hint at cellular signaling potential and sensitivity to external cues.
- Protein complexes: In cell biology, observing the spatial arrangement of certain protein complexes can shed light on cellular processes.
- The spatial organization of chromocenters within a nucleus can be described by point pattern ⁴²
- Single molecules resolved by Single Molecule Localisation Microscopy (SMLM) exhibit point patterns and are treated as point clouds to render their clusters and structures ⁴³.
- Within tissues, the centroids of cells, or the localisation of cell junctions generates a point pattern.
- The localisation of small organs or tissue within an enclosing organ or organism can be described through point patterns ⁴⁴.

Figure 4. Examples of structures that can be interpreted as point patterns. A) Stained cross section of a cervical biopsy, where the morphology of cells depends on the distance between their centroid and the organ boundary ⁴⁵. B) Quantitative analysis of spatial endocytic sites ⁴⁶. C) Analysis of 3D spatial organization of centromeres within nucleus ⁴². D) Dual labeling of thymidine analogies within *Fasciola hepatica* ⁴⁷. E) Schematic representation of dot objects together with various cases of hypothesis testing in a context of spatial transcriptomics ⁴⁸.

Porous media

Some biological structures such as portions of bone imaged at microscopic scale, or lung alveoli, present a "sponge-like" structure with a complex morphology that can be hardly described with classical region features.⁴⁹ The structure can be described through different approaches. One approach is to see the structure as the union of many individual elements at connecting nodes, such as the spicules of a glass sponge ⁵⁰. Another approach is to consider the population of pores or voids that may interconnect. It is also possible to see the image as a partition of the space into two or more phases, with a topologically complex interconnecting morphology. Note that this type of structure is more commonly encountered in material sciences, where the term porous media is widely encountered. The quantification of such images can rely on global geometric features, which are normalized by the size of the observation window, or more local geometric features such as local structure tensors.

Examples of porous media:

- Bone microstructure: They offer insights into bone strength and health.
- Lung tissue: interconnection between air and blood, with a large number of collapsing alveoli
- Plant mesophyll
- Foods such as bread and ice cream.
- Soils, which are important habitats for plant roots and microorganisms such as protozoa, bacteria and fungi.

Figure 5. Images of biological structures that can be interpreted as porous media. Trabecular bone (A) is an open-celled foam comprised mostly of collagen, hydroxyapatite mineral, and osteocytes. Here the intervening soft marrow tissue has been removed and the dry bone tissue imaged in scanning electron microscopy ⁵¹. (B) Spongy plant mesophyll has a porous structure, images here in X-ray microtomography ⁵². A photograph (C) and confocal scanning light microscopy image (D, red = oil, green = batter) demonstrate the porous structure and oil penetration depth in magwinya, a type of fried dough popular in South Africa and Botswana ⁵³. All images reused under CC-BY terms.

Texture image

In some cases, it may not be obvious to identify the structures of interest within images. The reasons may be that the resolution or the contrast is not sufficient to accurately identify the structure, or that the structure presents a large variability that is complicated to take into account. Instead of trying to identify the outline of a barely defined region, an alternative is to quantify the local variations of gray levels within neighbor pixels, by applying image texture analysis methods. This family of methods has proven powerful in medical imaging to describe changes between tissues or ROIs when the differences come mostly from fluctuations in the signal rather than from morphology or global intensity. Typical examples include detection of tumor from changes in texture features computed from MRI data ⁵⁴, from X-ray radiography images ^{55,56}, or ultrasound images ⁵⁷. Another common application is the detection of tumoral tissues from stained tissue sections, where the cells or nuclei may be difficult to identify. The approach can also be applied on images obtained from light or electron microscopy ⁵⁸. In particular, it may quantify patterned structures such as cell cytoskeleton even if individual elements can not be individualized ⁵⁹. The cellular morphology of plant tissues can be quantified at various scales even when cells can not be fully distinguished ^{60,61}. Texture analysis is also powerful to quantify topographic data such as obtained by atomic force microscopy.

Image texture features may be computed at different scales. At the larger scale, texture features may be computed on the whole image, and used to compare images. If regions have been identified within the image, texture features can be used to quantify variations of gray levels within regions. As texture features require a sufficient neighborhood for analysis, the size of the regions must be sufficiently large. At the pixel level, it is also possible to use the texture features computed around each pixel as input for pixel classification or segmentation approaches.

Examples of texture analysis:

- Tissue Sections: Evaluating different tissue types, especially in histology, where textural differences might hint at pathological changes or disease states. Additionally, in the field of cancer research identifying malignant from benign tumors based on texture irregularities, aids in cancer diagnosis and treatment studies.
- Cell Colonies: Differentiating between varying cell colonies in a Petri dish based on their growth patterns.

Figure 6: Examples of images illustrating the notion of image texture. (A) Discrimination of brains within MRI images (from ⁵⁴). (B) Study of wrist fractures from X-ray radiography images (from ⁵⁶). (C) Heart tissue slice imaged with high-resolution scanner (from ⁶²). (D) Cytoplasmic actin network (from ⁵⁹). (E) Changes of microstructure of grape cuticle observed with electron microscopy (from ⁶¹).

Dynamic structures

Any structures constituting biological systems are dynamic. They newly form, function, and disappear. The whole organism starts from an egg, grows, and then dies. We observe individual steps of these continuous processes and regard them as static entities. However this is just a matter of the duration of their existence, and we are often analyzing snapshots of those fully dynamic systems. In earlier imaging technology, the capturing of the time-lapse sequence was limited by hardware. Researchers did not have the technological capability to acquire hours and days of dynamic events at millimeter-scale in sufficiently high spatial resolution, or with high spatial and temporal resolution at the single-molecule level at nano-meter scale. As imaging technology has advanced constantly (e.g. single-molecule localization microscopy, single-plane illumination microscopy), we are now exploring more and more of those intrinsically dynamic systems.

The types of dynamics mostly inherit the types we have explained with static shapes: the time course of changes in regions, networks, point patterns, porous media, and texture. These features are measured at each time point and the time series of changes in these values represent those dynamics.

Examples of dynamic structures include:

- Organelle dynamics e.g. vesicle trafficking: Traffic of intracellular vesicles is studied to understand how cellular materials are endocytosed, transported, and exocytosed. A typical way of analyzing these dynamics is to measure the

changes in the amount of cargo proteins in different compartments within the cell or track each vesicle.

- Cytokinesis: Cytokinesis involves many elemental procedures including the determination of the division plane, membrane constrictions, separation of cellular materials, and cytoskeletal movements driving these shape changes.
- Chromosome dynamics: Separation of chromosomes is a key event during cell division, and how this genetically important process is orchestrated is often studied in terms of the formation of super-molecular structure connecting chromosomes and cytoskeleton, and cytoskeletal dynamics generating force to separate chromosomes.
- Cell migrations: Shape changes of cells are directly correlated with the migration of cells. In addition, understanding how cells navigate themselves toward a specific direction involves cell shape regulation by sensing environmental cues e.g. chemotaxis.
- Morphogenesis: during the development of multicellular structure, both in animals and plants, cells organize themselves to form the structure. The mechanism of this process is often analyzed by tracking cell movements and/or cell shape changes in relation to the overall morphogenetic movement.

How to identify the right category

Identification of the appropriate category for image analysis is not always a simple task. For example, depending on the type and the magnification of the acquisition device, neurons can be seen either as nearly convex regions (when considering the nuclear part), as a very ramified structure (when considering the surrounding dendrites), as a network of dendritic connections (when considering a population of neighbor neurons), or as a point pattern (when considering a slice of neuronal tissue).

This difficulty may become partially solved by keeping in mind that a specific type that a biologist chooses for a biological structure is a "Hypothesis". Rather than expecting that there is an intrinsic unique category that each biological structure belongs to, each researcher hypothesized that that biological structure belongs to a category. In another sense, this is like a modeling approach. For example, for single cells, we can hypothesize that each cell occupies a certain area. This is taking the cell with an "area region model", so to say, to measure certain properties of dynamics observable within the cell. Alternatively, we can hypothesize that a single cell is "a point", for example, the centroid of the cell area, if we want to measure the position of that cell. In this case, we are taking a "point model" for cells. Hence, it is important to keep in mind that how we categorize biological structures depends firstly on how that shape visually appears, which is dependent on the magnification and the optics we use for imaging, and secondly on the goal of the measurement we want to achieve. For this second point, knowledge of what we can do with digital image processing and analysis is important. We explain this in the following section.

Types of image analysis approaches

In order to facilitate linking biological questions to image analysis, we present here an overview of various image analysis approaches according to the different types of structures presented in the previous section. For each approach, we provide examples of biological application.

Region Analysis

A widely used approach in image analysis is to identify the relevant regions within the image, and to compute for each of them a set of quantitative region features. Such features may describe the morphology of regions, but also the values of pixels within regions, including intensity, color or texture. In some cases, the spatial organization of regions may be quantified. Based on the computed features, machine learning approaches can be applied to identify groups of similar regions, or build discriminative models.

Morphology

A typical way to describe regions is to quantify their morphology. The **morphometry** can be defined as the measurement of the morphology, comprising size and shape features ^{2,3,7,63}. The most straightforward approach to quantify the morphology is to compute size and shape features from the regions.

For regions retrieved from two-dimensional images, typical size features comprise the area, the perimeter, diameters (Ferret diameter, geodesic diameter...). Morphology features may be computed from a derived region such as the convex hull, the bounding box or the enclosing disc. The computation of inertia moments is also of common use, and can be easily interpreted through an equivalent ellipse with same moments up to the second order. Counterparts are often easily defined for three-dimensional regions (volume, surface area, equivalent ellipsoid...). The "width" or the "thickness" may also be related to the size, while their definitions are less consensual: diameter of largest inscribed disk, width of the oriented bounding box, average thickness computed over a medial axis within the region, etc.

It is often desirable to quantify morphology of regions independently of their position, size, or orientation. Within the domain of **shape analysis**, a large number of shape features have been defined in order to be invariant with isometries. Such features are most of the time based on (normalized) ratios of features that quantify the size. Typical examples comprise elongation, circularity, roundness, convexity. Note that the definitions often differ depending on authors or on communities ^{6,7}. For three-dimensional regions, similar shape indices may be defined as well ^{42,64,65}. For

example, measuring the elongation of a sphere-like structure in a tissue can give hints to physical stresses present between the cells in the tissue ⁶⁶.

More complex shape features may be obtained by considering a parameterisation of the contour. The polar signature corresponds to the function of the distance to the closest boundary point from a reference point, in the direction given by the angle. A more generic approach consists in applying harmonic analysis by computing the Fourier transform of the x and y projections of the contour, leading to **Elliptic Fourier Descriptors** ^{63,67-69}. Three-dimensional regions can be analyzed in a similar way using spherical harmonics ⁷⁰⁻⁷². Such harmonic analysis furthermore makes it possible to quantify curvatures on the region boundary ^{73,74}. For regions with complex boundaries, the notion of fractal dimension also allows quantifying this complexity ^{75,76}.

When regions are elongated, it is also common to focus on the **medial axis** of the shape, and to assimilate the region to a curve. Medial axis can be retrieved through a skeletonisation algorithm. Relevant morphological features include curve length, average thickness, and shape factors such as tortuosity. It is often informative to consider the variations of some features along the curve: thickness curvature, or orientation. In the case of time-lapse images, this leads to kinematic analysis of growth ^{77,78}. In the case of elongated regions, the orientation of the regions, relative to each other or to a reference structure, may also be considered ⁶⁴.

Regions may also have more complex shapes, presenting invagination, disjoint parts, and/or holes within parts. In such cases, the **topology of the region** may be of interest. Topology is typically described by the Euler number, which quantifies the number of "handles" of the structure. In the case of very complex topology, considering the structure as a network can sometimes be more relevant (see below). The skeleton of the region may also be of interest. Using the skeleton makes it possible to also consider the morphometry of individual branches (length, thickness, curvature...).

In anatomy, physiology, or developmental biology, regions correspond to well-known structures (bones, skulls, specific organisms...). They may have highly complex morphology that is difficult to describe with few summary features. The allometric approach consists in identifying a set of **landmarks** that correspond to characteristic points, and quantifying the shape by computing the ratios of distances between pairs of landmarks ⁷⁹⁻⁸¹. More generally, the computational anatomy approach considers describing populations of shapes by projecting them into an abstract "shape space", and computing distances between shapes (or populations of shapes) within this space ⁸². While originally developed in a context of medical imaging, the methods can be applied to other biological domains as well ⁸³.

Intensity and texture features

Regions are not defined only by their morphology, and the values of pixels or voxels within the regions may also be of interest. In the case of monochromatic images (i.e. gray levels or intensity images), the average intensity of pixels within the region can be used as an additional feature to describe the region. Other summary statistics such as the variance or the standard deviation of gray levels can also be used to quantify homogeneity or heterogeneity of intensities within regions. More specific features can be obtained from the study of local variations of intensities or gray levels within each region. This is the aim of image texture analysis (see the corresponding section hereafter). In the case of color images, features can be computed for each channel independently.

Spatial organization of regions / neighborhood relationships

In addition to the morphology or the intensity features, the spatial organization of the regions is also of particular interest. Indeed, the regions are often interpreted depending on their relative location to a reference region: the boundary of the enclosing cell or organ, its center, a specific anatomical point, etc. Regions can be at the periphery, in the center, close to an extremity... This kind of spatial relationship can be addressed by computing the distance between the regions (or of their centroid) with the reference structure, and interpreting regions features according to this distance. It is also possible to analyze regions depending on whether they are included within the reference region(s), in a "parent-child" relationship⁸⁴. The "mereotopology" approach, originally developed to enhance segmentation, aims at describing more formally how several regions are organized together, e.g. A is on the left of B, B is within C... (Bloch, 1999; Landini et al., 2019; Randell et al., 2013).

When analyzing images of plant tissues composed of many cells, one can also consider a topological distance, by counting the number of cells one has to travel through in order to reach the reference region. This type of analysis requires the construction of a region adjacency graph (RAG) between the regions, where the nodes of the graph correspond to the regions, and the edges denote a pair of adjacent regions. The use of region adjacency graph allows for using graph-theory methods, such as computation of shortest paths between relevant regions. Dedicated software have been developed for the construction and analysis of such graphs^{88,89}.

The adjacency between regions is also useful to analyze the features of a region in relation to those of its neighbors. Indeed, cells may be associated to a specific tissue or cell layer, such as the epidermis, or to groups of cells arising from successive divisions⁹⁰⁻⁹³. Typical questions are the identification of groups of similar and adjacent regions, or the relationships between the (morphometric) features of a region and that of its neighbors. Physical information may be associated with nodes or edges of the graph. For example, cells exchange information via chemical signals and physical stresses that can be associated with the corresponding edges.

Another concept related to spatial organization is the relative orientation of regions, as the orientation of a given structure or region is often determined relative to another structure used as reference ⁶⁴. The quantification of orientation is mostly relevant for thin and elongated structures, and flat structures in three-dimensions. Orientation can also be quantified locally, using operators based on Hessian matrix or structure tensor ⁹⁴. Note that when considering patterns of thin and parallel structures, the tools from image texture analysis may also be of interest.

When analyzing spatial-omics data, also neighborhood-relationships between cells or data points are considered to make sense of data sets with a large number of channels ⁹⁵. Combining analysis techniques using cell adjacency graphs, gene expression and classical imaging data analysis can be tackled using modern machine learning approaches ⁹⁶.

Classification of regions

Once a number of features have been quantified within a collection of regions, several machine learning approaches are possible. It is first necessary to organize quantitative features into a data table, where the rows correspond to the regions, and the columns to the features. Each individual region is therefore embedded into a multi-dimensional "shape-space" defined by the collection of features. The combination of dimension reduction and unsupervised learning (clustering) allows the identification of populations of regions that share similar features.^{30,69,97} When regions have been associated to groups, one may apply analysis of variance to test differences in morphology, intensity or texture. Another option is to build a machine learning classifier that will identify which group (e.g. "healthy" or "unhealthy") each region belongs to^{73,98}.

Networks

The quantification of network-like structure requires identification of the branches and junction points. This can often be performed by first applying a classical segmentation procedure, followed by a "skeletonization" operation, that will thin all the structures such that the width will be one pixel. Once skeletonized, it becomes possible to identify junctions, branches, and eventually end-points. The topology of the network can then be described by using tools from graph theory: number of loops, distribution of number of branches crossing at a given node... . For example, quantifying the number of branches in neuronal development can hint towards modified development and disease ⁹⁹. In ophthalmology and developmental studies of vascular systems, the vasculature network is described by a variety of approaches including fractal dimension, skeleton density, lacunarity analysis, or tortuosity ^{36,37,100}. Plant root branching adapts to available resources such as water and soil, exposing different scientific questions that can be approached with similar analysis strategies ^{101,102}. Practical steps to analyze tumor blood vessel networks using Fiji have been reported for the diagnosis of the progression of cancer ¹⁰³.

Quantitative features may be attached to nodes or edges, for example the thickness or the length of the edges ¹⁰⁴. Analysis can then be performed by extracting statistics for the different components (branch length histogram).

Topological features may also be analyzed with respect to their location. For example, in neuron research, a classical analysis consists in counting intersections of dendrites with concentric circles of increasing radius ^{105,106}. In plant sciences, Herremans et al. (2015) studied the number of branching points of a fruit vasculature network with respect to the distance to the fruit center ³⁸.

Point patterns

In the case of point patterns, objects are defined solely by their position. Methods from spatial statistics have been developed to describe quantitatively point patterns independently of what they represent: position of trees, cell centroids, stars in a galaxy, etc. ¹⁰⁷ The features to quantify are not related to the size or the shape, but to the notions of density and spatial organization. The interest in this family of methods recently increased with the development of spatial omics ^{48,89,95,108}. A common use-case for related techniques is counting DNA double strand breaks imaged in one channel and associating them with a nuclei-segmentation from another channel, e.g. in cancer research ¹⁰⁹.

A first way to describe point patterns is to identify regions where points are the most numerous. A typical solution for this is to compute density maps that associate to each pixel of the map the expected number of points in the neighborhood. Density maps can be computed by applying signal processing tools such as Parzen filters, or by relating the distance to the k-th nearest point. Density maps can then be investigated with image analysis tools. They may be related to a distance map to a biological structure to investigate organization with respect to that structure ^{44,45,110}.

In the case of imaging of proteins with different emission spectra, resulting images present point patterns into two different channels. A large number of methods have been proposed to quantify the colocalization of the two families of proteins, based on the overlap of the dots ^{111,112}.

Point patterns may also exhibit spatial interactions, such as attraction or repulsion. Tools from spatial statistics are of high interest to quantify such interactions. A family of methods rely on summary functions that quantify the degree of interaction depending on a given distance. The most common one is the "K-function", introduced by Ripley, that counts the expected number of points within a disk of radius r centered on a typical point ¹¹³. Deviations from a quadratic count denote an aggregation (clustering) or on the contrary a repulsion effect at a given distance between the points. Several variants have been proposed (the L-function, H-function, F-function...) to facilitate the interpretation ⁴⁶. Note that the result of the analysis is a function, thus requiring further investigations and possibly analysis to draw a conclusion.

As a complement of quantification from summary functions, the domain of stochastic geometry has proposed various models to represent geometric patterns. For point patterns, such models randomly generate synthetic point patterns with organization similar to that of the observations, in a similar way random values can be generated using a pre-defined number distribution (Normal, Poisson...).

Porous media

When considering porous media, the quantification of morphology may be difficult to apprehend, as there is no obvious "region" to relate to, and classical morphological features can not be easily applied. However, several approaches have been proposed to quantify morphology of porous media, most of them originating from material sciences ¹¹⁴⁻¹¹⁶. A first approach can be to identify elementary components of either the solid or the void phase, and quantify the distribution of a given size feature computed on the components. The components may be the individual grains that form the structure, the elementary voids or empty spaces between solid components, or the struts or plates that join more compact elements ¹¹⁷. For example the thickness of the struts or plates can be related to the overall stiffness or solidity, or the diameter of the pores can be related to diffusion properties. However, the elementary elements may be difficult or impossible to individualize, and it is often necessary to consider more global characterization of the microstructures. In particular, the notion of connectivity, related to the percolation phenomenon, is often of specific interest ¹¹⁸. A related concept is the tortuosity, often based on the computation of a geodesic distance ¹¹⁸⁻¹²⁰. The notion of "size" can be computed either along the skeleton of the structure, or averaged over all the pixels or voxels that compose it. The thickness often appears as a key descriptive feature, and can be obtained by computing locally maximal disks or balls ^{118,121}. Descriptive features based on covariance can also provide a global quantification of the media ¹²². Other features have been proposed to quantify the variations of thickness with respect to the orientation. Several software have been developed to facilitate the diffusion of such methods ^{20,123-125}.

Image texture analysis

Several approaches have been considered for quantification of image texture ¹²⁶. Maybe the most popular one is the notion of gray-level co-occurrence matrices, that describes the second-order image histogram by computing the probability that a pixel with a given value is at a given distance from a pixel with another value. ¹²⁶⁻¹²⁸ The run-length matrix approach is an alternative that decomposes images into elementary runs of consecutive pixels with constant or similar gray values ¹²⁹. Image texture may also be investigated by applying image transforms to better identify relevant features. Examples include Fourier transform, wavelets, or Gabor transform ¹³⁰. Some techniques build predictive models of gray level variations, using for example autoregressive models, or markov random fields, and use parameters of the model as texture descriptors. Within the domain of mathematical morphology, the gray level

granulometry approach results in pattern spectrum curves that can be interpreted in the same way as classical size distributions^{60,131,132}.

Dynamic structures

Analysis of dynamic structures involves studying changes and movements in biological structures over time, often captured through live-cell imaging or time-lapse microscopy. The analysis provides mechanistic insights into their biological processes by examining the effect of drug treatment, genetic perturbations, and environmental differences such as temperature and chemical gradients on structural dynamics for physiological studies and phenotyping.

Tracking determines the position change of the target structure over time and is a widely used image analysis approach for measuring the movements. In many cases, the shape of the target structure is diminished to a point by image processing e.g. centroid, representing the position of the structure^{133,134}. This procedure is often called “detection”. These detected points are then linked over time using various algorithms, especially to avoid mistakes in linking different dots and to accommodate vanishing and newly appearing dots, to estimate movement trajectories. This process is called “linking”^{135–138}. In the case of near-spherical objects such as intracellular vesicles, their detection resembles dot detection algorithms. For more complex shapes such as single cells, the geometric centroid is often used to represent the cell position (Figure 1).

Basic movement features such as trajectories, velocities, and directionalities are computed from tracking results. To avoid the bias of sampling interval on the estimated velocity, tracks can be analyzed using mean-square displacement (MSD) plots, which allows the estimation of the activities of random movement and biased (directed) movement separately¹³⁹. For small spherical structures, a well-known diffusion equation can be curve-fitted to the MSD plot, and the inclusion of the anomalous exponent, α , to the equation allows the estimation of the diffusive behavior with steric hindrance or with active transport^{140–142}. For more complex shapes such as cells, Fuert’s formula, which incorporates the assumption of random movement intervened by persistent movement, is recommended for fitting MSD plots^{143–145}. Significant bias in the movement suggests a certain directionality of movement, and for deriving a proper statistical measure of directed movement, circular statistics is recommended^{146,147}.

The measurement of curvilinear regions’ dynamics are also a type of tracking. The algorithms used are different from particle tracking and application-specific. In plants, the growth of hypocotyl and roots has been measured by reducing their shape to curvilinear regions using skeletonization and by matching skeleton positions between successive frames to determine the zones of active growth and curvature formation^{77,78,148,149}. Dynamic instability of microtubules is measured using various algorithms

such as active contour ¹⁵⁰ and Gaussian fitting ^{151,152} to automatically delineate their curvilinear structure. Filopodia are thin and elongated structures protruding from cells exhibiting extension, bending, and shrinking. They can be analyzed by segmenting actin filaments within filopodia for measuring length statistics, protrusion velocity, curvature, and correlation with protein localizations within filopodia, among other dynamics features ^{153,154}.

Cell migration studies offer great examples of measuring the shape changes of regions as contour shape dynamics. A general approach for segmenting cell contour is intensity thresholding and binarization ^{155,156}. A more robust approach less affected by intensity variations at the cell edge is active contour algorithms to automatically delineate cell contour for quantitative analysis of cell edge advancement and retractions ^{157–159}.

Kymograph is an approach that does not depend on the shape of the target structure ^{160–163}. A line of pixels at a specified position within the image frame is sampled sequentially over time and stacked on a two-dimensional kymograph with the one axis being space and the other being time. In this way, various dynamics, especially those that are difficult to segment can be measured for the speed of the movement, for example with proteins ¹⁶⁴. Kymographs can also represent the evolution of a given quantity along a curvilinear structure, by using the curvilinear abscissa for the space coordinate ^{77,165}.

Shape changes are often studied how their constituting elements are driving those changes. Tissue morphogenesis is studied by analyzing cell shape changes, migrations, and force generations ¹⁶⁶. Cell migrations are analyzed by intracellular cytoskeletal dynamics ¹⁶⁷. Protein localization patterns are studied by protein-protein interaction kinetics and active transports. With transiently appearing or disappearing structures such as endocytic vesicles that appear during endocytosis, autophagosomes during autophagy, or the midbody during cytokinesis, analysis of protein dynamics during the formation of those structures has been the key to understand the process of the formation of those structures. These image analyses of dynamics at two different size scales provide powerful hints to their causal relationships. Such inference can be further nailed down by combining mathematical modelings ^{168,169}.

Towards a decision tree for bio-image analysis

The different questions and concepts addressed within this article can be summarized in Figure 7. For the sake of simplicity, we have chosen not to include the time dimension within the decision tree. Starting from an image of a biological specimen, the first questions consist of identifying the type of structure that is the most appropriate to describe it: region(s), point pattern, network, porous media, or texture image. Depending on this type, a variety of features can be envisioned. They are

represented as rectangles in the figure. To quantify the morphology of regions, the relevant features have to be chosen according to the complexity of the region: rather compact, mostly linear, or providing a complex morphology.

Figure 7. Decision tree for identifying families of image analysis methods depending on the type of structure within the image.

Conclusions

In conclusion, advancing the field of bioimaging necessitates fostering a collaborative environment where biologists and image analysts share a common language and understanding. Our study highlights the importance of simplifying the bridge between complex bioimage datasets and the extraction of meaningful biological data. By categorizing biological structures and linking them to appropriate analysis methods, we provide a valuable resource for early career scientists and researchers. This approach not only aids in selecting suitable analysis techniques but also fosters better communication between biologists and image analysts. Our flowchart serves as a practical tool, simplifying the complex process of bioimage analysis and enhancing the ability to extract meaningful insights from biological data. Ultimately, this work aims to streamline bioimage analysis workflows, making advanced techniques more approachable and effective for diverse research applications.

Acknowledgements

EF acknowledges support by Biomedicum Imaging Unit, Helsinki University and HiLife, as a part of Biocenter Finland infrastructure. RH acknowledges the financial support by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research of Germany and by Sächsische

Staatsministerium für Wissenschaft, Kultur und Tourismus in the programme Center of Excellence for AI-research „Center for Scalable Data Analytics and Artificial Intelligence Dresden/Leipzig“, project identification number: ScaDS.AI.

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